

THE EFFICACY OF WORLD FOOD PROGRAM TO THE PUPILS' PERFORMANCE: BINIDAYAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL EXPERIENCE

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The Efficacy of World Food Program to the Pupils' Performance: Binidayan Elementary School Experience

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the efficacy of the World Food Program to the pupils' performance of Binidayan Elementary School. This study utilized the descriptive qualitative, in which there were thirty (30) randomly selected Grades IV to VI pupils in Binidayan Elementary School, Binidayan District, Lanao del Sur II, ARMM. Findings revealed that the World Food Program has an effect on the increased of the academic performance, the behavior, the attendance, the nutritional status, and the enrollment of the respondent. There was no significant relationship between the status of World Food Program implementation to the academic performance, behavior, attendance, nutritional status (BMI) and enrollment of the respondent. One of the primary goals of World Food Programs was to provide meals or snacks to reduce short-term hunger in the classroom so that the students can concentrate and learned better, and to attract children to school and have them attend class regularly. An action plan is recommended to be followed to sustain the World Food Program.

Keywords: *efficacy, education, social science, world food program, teaching, approach, descriptive-correlational research design, Philippines*

Introduction

True to the provision of the constitution, basic education is free. Despite free education, hunger was the hindrance for students to be attentive in the classroom. Pupils in the remote areas do not experience the three times a day meal that is why even if they are eager to learn, they still cannot focus because of empty stomach. Hunger is a barrier to learning. A hungry child is less likely to concentrate, less likely to perform well at school, and more likely to drop out. Enrollment in Binidayan Elementary school was reported that many students were at risk of dropping out. Hunger, illness, frequent truancy, lack of school requirements are among other factors that have been reported as the causes of poor enrollment and high dropout rates in schools at rural areas of Lanao del sur. Thus, the quality of education of the pupils suffers.

The mission of the World Food Program is to end global hunger. Every day, World Food Program works worldwide to ensure that no child goes to be hungry and that the power of and most vulnerable, particularly women and children can access the nutritious food the need. World Food Program (WFP) will seek to purchase food for school feeding cannot only improve children's ability to concentrate and learn by addressing short-term food insecurity and reducing micronutrient deficiencies when food is fortified, but also increases school enrollment and attendance particularly for girls and provide a significant income transfer to vulnerable families through take-home rations. It can serve as a powerful platform for complementary health interventions provided by others including deworming.

School feeding was assumed as a measure to address the problem of students' enrollment and dropout in some hunger prone regions in the country. The available empirical studies show that school feeding has positively contributed to students' enrollment and reduced students' dropout in primary schools in many developing countries (Jomaa et al., 2011). Although the available studies may show that school feeding programs have contributed to students' enrollment and reduction of students' dropout rate. They are limited in some cases and most of them were done in developed countries, and few were done in Africa (Oganga, 2013).

Every day, WFP and its partners work to bring us closer to a zero-hunger world. With our humanitarian food assistance, we provide nutritious food to those in urgent need. Meanwhile, our complementary programs address the root causes of hunger, building the resilience of communities, so we do not need to keep saving the same lives each year.

The world has made great progress in reducing hunger: There are 216 million fewer hungry people than in 1990-92, despite a 1.9 billion increase in the world's population. But there is still a long way to go, and no single organization can achieve Zero Hunger if it works alone. If we want to see the world free of hunger by 2030, governments, citizens, civil society organizations and the private sectors must collaborate to invest, innovate, and create lasting solutions. The objectives of the WFP's school feeding program are to increase students' enrollment, attendance, and concentration span among school children. It also intends to increase their learning capacity, reduce dropout rates, and gender disparity in primary schools.

However, proper intake of nutrients aids in efficient functioning of the brain and other body organs. Thus, good nutrient helps pupils learn ideas and retain useful information in the brain (Bryan, Osendarp, Hughes, Calvaresi, Bagusrst, & Van Kinken, 2004) Basing the views from nutrition experts, pupils with normal nutritional status show up at school prepared to learn. Because of improved nutrition, all these make pupils healthier, have fewer absences and attend classes more frequently (Clamonte-Alolor 2016).

The study will examine school feeding baselines surveys and other needs assessments, targeting of school feeding, choices of operational modalities and implementing arrangements, including partnerships, the monitoring and evaluation of school feeding, and

the cost of running school feeding programmers. For assessing effectiveness, the evaluation will consider information concerning all operations that have included a school feeding component in the 8 months' period from July through March.

As an elementary graded teacher and assigned in the area, the researcher investigates the efficacy of world food program to the pupils' performance, views of the parents, children, and teachers on the effectiveness of school feeding program, particularly on its effect to increase students' enrollment, and on the maintaining of students' retention, as well as the program's sustainability in Binidayan Elementary school, Binidayan, Lanao del sur.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the point-of-view of the efficacy of World Food Program (WFP) to the pupils. It also aimed to incorporate views or perceptions of students, teachers, and parents on what did they considered the contributions of the programs to pupil's attendance, retention, and the future of the program's sustainability. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the status of implementation of the World Food Program (WFP) in terms of:
 - 1.1. Duration; and
 - 1.2. frequency?
2. What are the effects of World Food Program to the pupils in terms of:
 - 2.1. academic performances,
 - 2.2. behaviors,
 - 2.3. attendance, and
 - 2.4. nutritional status?
3. What action plan can be formulated to sustain the feeding program?

Methodology

Research Design

The method used in this study was the descriptive-correlational research design. Moreover, this study also used qualitative methods because the data were based on the effect of the World Food Program on the pupils' Academic performance, attendance, and their behavior. RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT This study was conducted in Binidayan Elementary School, Binidayan District, Binidayan, Lanao Del Sur. Binidayan Elementary School teachers through Republic Act 9575, teach pupils from kindergarten to Grade 6 in Binidayan, Lanao Del Sur of Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM). The school has four buildings with fifteen (15) instructional rooms and one (1) non-instructional room with no reliable source of power. The school has nineteen (19) teachers including the subject teachers and three (3) ALIVE teachers. In addition, the school has a kitchen for the feeding program donated by the parents of the pupils and a two doors comfort room for the pupils. The school has a wide playground, enough for the pupils to do their school activity.

Binidayan is a fourth-class municipality in the province of Lanao del Sur, Philippines. According to the 2015 census, it has a population of 22,079 people. Binidayan is politically subdivided into 26 barangays namely, Badak, Baguiangun, Maito a Balut, Basak, Bubong Cabasaran, Bubonga Ranao, Dansalan, Dacsula, Kialilidan, Lumbac, Macaguiling, Madaya, Magonaya, Maindig, Masolun, Bario Olama, Pagalamatan, Pantar, Picalilangan, Picotaan, Pindolonan, Poblacion, Soldaroro, Tambac, Timbangan and Tuca.

Furthermore, Lanao Del Sur is the land of the Maranaos, "People of the lake," among the most devout of Muslim tribes as well as the most artistic. Nowhere is this evident than in the people's most natural way of life and land's most attractive sites. Lake Lanao, the second largest and deepest lake in the Philippines is one of the most breathtakingly beautiful surrounded with myths and legends. The climate here is invigorating and fine grazing land stretches into the distance. Situated in the interior of Lanao Del Sur is Lanao Lake, the largest in Mindanao. The Darangen Epic Chants of the Maranao of Lanao del Sur is inscribed as a UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage since 2008.

Participants

Table 1. Represents the following distributions of participants

	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Pupils			
Grade 4	5	5	10
Grade 5	5	5	10
Grade 6	5	5	10
Teacher	0	3	3
Total	15	18	33

The respondents of the study were thirty (30) pupils from Grade 4 to Grade 6 in Binidayan Elementary School. In this case, the researcher chosen (10) pupils in every grade level from Binidayan Elementary School, Binidayan District Lanao del Sur during the

school year 2017-2018. The participants of the study were randomly selected with the use of "Fish and Bowl" technique, a type of probability which selects member of the sample proportioned from each population. This was how advisers selected pupils as the participants in this study and they recommended ten (10) pupils who were under the feeding program.

Instruments

The study utilized a research-made interview question. The interview questions consisted of three parts:

Part I the status of WFP implementation in terms of duration and frequency of feeding program as to the year of before and after implementation and the numbers of pupils being fed from the adviser.

Part II is on the effect of the World Food Program implementation in terms Data from of the academic performance, behavior, attendance, nutritional status, and enrollment. This part dealt with the records of the pupils from the advisers in terms of the academic performance, behavior, attendance, and nutritional status of the pupils while the enrollment came from the principal records from school Year 2016-2017 To 2017-2018.

Part III dealt with the implications and recommendations drawn from the result of the study. Information was collected from the participants as the researcher interviewed them.

Procedure

The researcher was the one personally met the participants of the study to facilitate the gathering of data about the school feeding sponsored by World Food Program. The researcher asked permission from the School's Principal and the parents of the respondents together with the letter signed and approved by the research adviser in order to visit the school and to conduct the study.

The School Feeding Program started at the month of July 2016 and ended on March 2017. Every day the participants were provided with breakfast during recess time. Food composed of rice, mongos/beans and some donated fish from the teachers and parents. The funds and resources were provided by the World Food Program. The food preparation was done by the volunteer parents with their given schedules.

The data gathered through the following: Academic performance (Pupils Report Card), Behavioral Records (from the advisers/Guidance Counselor), Daily Attendance Report of Learners (from the advisers in SF 2), Nutritional Status (from the class adviser), and Enrolment Data (from the School Principal).

Data Analysis

The statistical tool used in this study for Problems 1 and 2 were frequency and percentage to describe the data of the study. These were the tools used in describing the status of implementation of the World Food Program (WFP) in terms of duration and frequency. The same statistical tools were used to describe the effects of World Food Program to the pupils in terms of Academic performance, behavior, attendance, nutritional status, and enrolment.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the analysis, results, and discussions of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1. What is the status of implementation of the World Food Program (WFP) in terms of duration and frequency?

Table 2. The Duration of the implementation of World Food Program

Pupils	Duration					
	Before the implementation SY 2016-2017 (July-March)			Before the implementation SY 2016-2017 (July-November)		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Teacher/Class Adviser	15	15	30	15	15	30
	0	3	3	0	3	3
	Total:		33			33

Table 2 elaborates the status of implementation in terms of duration. Specifically, before the implementation of the World Food Program in school year 2016-2017 (July-March), there were thirty (30) pupil-participants and 3 teachers/class advisers. The same participants were conducted after the implementation of the World Food Program in school year 2017-2018 (July- November).

The teachers chosen as participants for the interview were recommended by the School Principal with the most active participation during the feeding activities. They have also recorded on the different behavior of the pupil- participants observed during the feeding activities. The same group of pupil-participants was conducted during the post implementation of the World Food Program.

The teachers also shared how eager the pupils were to ask if there is another feeding activity in the next school year. It simply showed that pupils enjoyed the program. They shared happy and funny moments together while they were eating. The teachers and the parents

willfully participated in the feeding activity every day even if they have also other things to attend to. Amidst the busy schedule of the parents at home, they were motivated by the sacrifices made by the teachers and the eagerness showed by their children. That's why the parents continued to support their children and assist the teachers all throughout the feeding activity. After the whole implementation of the World months Food Program, the teachers, parents, and the pupil-participants galvanized and feeding activity that built strong relationship together. Furthermore, teachers and parents observed the changes manifested by the pupil-participants after the school feeding activity. There was an increase of their grades and they demonstrated the value of helping their classmates. The teachers and the parents showed satisfaction with the results, and they were thankful that they were part of the improvement and development of their children in the school.

Table 3. *The Frequency of the implementation of World Food Program to the participants*

Month of Implementation	No. of days	Feeding Days	% of Implementation
July	21	(Takeout)	0%
August	20	20	100%
September	20	20	100%
October	21	17	80.95%
November	21	17	80.95%
December	15	12	100%
January	22	18	81.82%
February	20	16	80.00%
March	22	22	100%
Total	182	145	

Table 3 presents the frequency of the implementation of the World Food Program to the participants. It indicates that the program was employed almost every day from the month of July 2016 to March 2017 particularly in the months of August, September, and March. Teachers assured that the feeding activity must be implemented every day and obliged the parents as representatives to be present on their scheduled day. There were also months wherein the school feeding was not fully implemented because of holidays and other activities. These were the months of October, November, December, January and February. There was no implementation of the feeding activity in the month of July due to the Ramadhan days wherein 100% of the pupils were Muslims. The parents, the pupils and some of the teachers performed the fasting. So, the PTA officers and teachers and with the approval of the School Principal, agreed to distribute the food supply of 1 cup of rice and 4 of mongos to the pupils every Sunday of the week for the entire month of July.

The World Food Program informed us ahead of their upcoming visits. During their visit, they interviewed the parents on how they prepared and cooked the food. They inspected the utensils such as the 6 big stock pots and the 3 big pans if these were being used. They also checked if the toilets were clean and had an abundant water supply. They also checked the school garden to see if it was planted with vegetables to supply the feeding activity. Being a recipient of this kind of program was an honor for the school as they heard there were only some who were chosen to be the recipients of the program.

Problem 2. What are the effects of the World Food Program (WFP) to the pupils in terms of academic performances, behaviors, attendance, nutritional status, and enrollment?

Table 4. *Academic performance of the participants before and after the implementations of World Food Program*

Rage	Level	Male		Female		Indicator
		Before	After	Before	After	
90-above	Outstanding	1	3	3	5	Increasing
85-89	Very Satisfactory	8	8	6	7	Increasing
80-84	Satisfactory	5	4	4	3	Increasing
75-79	Fair Satisfactory	1	0	2	0	Increasing
74 below	Did not Meet Expectation (74 and below)	0	0	0	0	None
Total		15	15	15	15	Increasing

Table 4 presents the distribution of academic performance of the participants before and after the implementation of the World food Program. The result indicates that there was a change in the academic performance of the participants before the implementation of the program. There was 1 male and 3 female out of 15 participants were on the Outstanding Level. This meant that only a few reached the high grade. There were 8 males and 6 females out of 15 participants were on the Very Satisfactory Level. This showed that almost of the participants reached this level. There were 5 males and 4 females out of 15 participants were on the Satisfactory Level and only 1 male and 2 female out of 15 were on the Fairly Satisfactory Level. None of them got 74 and below.

After the implementation of the World Food Program as shown in table 5, the participants increased their academic performance. From 1 became 3 for the males as teachers said, "there were pupils who tried their best to excel in the class as they were competent compared with the female classmates". Although there were some who were still at satisfactory and fairly satisfactory levels. Teachers observed

that the participants were eager to learn and improve in the class. Their tardiness was gone, and now they listened to their teachers attentively. While for the female participants from 3 to 5 highest level or 2/3 reached the Outstanding Level. The researcher asked the teachers about the records of the 5 pupils, and it showed a positive feedback. The 5 pupils manifested good study habits like reading books and their thinking skill was improved. There were 7 out of 15 pupils who were at Very Satisfactory Level, which was not quite bad. It implied that almost half of the female participants reached this level and only few were in Satisfactory Level. The teachers said that these pupils lived in far places about 25-30 minutes hiking hours. This is the reason why sometimes they were tired when they got to school and even late in their classes. The academic performance of the participants on their post implementation program was based on their second grading average grade of this school year 2017-2018. In this connection, teachers were challenged to find the best techniques to address academic performance improvement as the results implied that only half of one-fourths got the outstanding level even after the feeding program was implemented. They were having a forum with their co-teachers regarding the performance of their pupils.

Table 5. Behavior of the participants before and after the implementation of World Food Program

Recorded common untoward incident/behavior	Male		Female		Indicator
	Before	After	Before	After	
B1 Disrespecting teachers	2	0	1	0	Decreasing
B2 Running away from the class	2	0	1	0	Decreasing
B3 Disobedience	2	0	2	0	Decreasing
B4 Playing while the class is ongoing	3	0	3	0	Decreasing
B5 Having disruptive conversation	4	0	2	0	Decreasing
B6 Shouting	2	0	1	0	Decreasing
B7 non-attentiveness	4	1	2		Decreasing
B8 Tardiness an	1	0	2	0	Decreasing
B9 Day dreaming	3	0	0	1	Decreasing
B10 Eating and drinking	2	0	0	0	Decreasing
B11 Habitual failure in submitting assignments	2	0	0	0	Decreasing
B12 Destroying things in the classroom	2	0	1	0	Decreasing
B13 Speaking foul language	1	0	1	0	Decreasing
B14 Quarrelling	1	0	0	0	Decreasing
B15 Rudeness	1	0	1	0	Decreasing

Table 6 presents the participants behavioral records from the guidance counselor/adviser before and after the implementation of the World Food Program. The result displayed that almost of the recorded untoward incident/behavior of the respondent decreased after the school feeding, while there were only some of the participants who had a record of misbehavior which was most commonly happened in classroom setting. Before the implementation of the program, pupils had a list of recorded common incident/behavior observed by the teachers. Individual teacher mentioned that running away from the class, disobedience, playing while the class is ongoing, having disruptive conversation, daydreaming, inattentive, out of seat, eating and drinking, habitual failure in submitting assignments, and tardiness were recorded as unacceptable behavior of the pupils, mainly because these behaviors affect the pupils learning and classroom atmosphere.

Furthermore, disrespecting the teacher or refusing to follow instructions was disobedient and disrespectful behavior. As the researcher interviewed the pupils involved, he said "Di aken bo di taroon so katawan aken na di ako nyan pamakinegenn na geoto badn a di aken mambo pamakinegen skanian", which means (I just want to share what I know but he does not listen to me, so I did not listen to her either). Destroying things in the classroom was one of the major offenses recorded in the classroom. Teachers observed that some pupils nowadays were rebellious, and they behaved the other way around. They won't listen to the teachers.

On the other hand, after the implementation of the World Food Program, the participants rarely misbehaved in the classroom/school premises. Positive behaviors were observed from them like listening to their teachers, following do's and don'ts in the classroom, respecting others, helping and etc. This implied that the implementation of this program played a significant role in the changes of behavior of the pupils.

Table 6. Attendance of the participants before and after the implementations of World Food Program (based on their absences on the SF2)

Pupils	Male		Female		Indicator
	S.Y 2016-2017	S.Y 2017-2018	S.Y 2016-2017	S.Y 2017-2018	
Grade IV	20	2	16	2	Decreasing
Grade V	24	3	16	2	Decreasing
Grade VI	19	1	13	1	Decreasing

Table 6 presents the attendance of the participants before and after the implementation of the World Food Program (based on their absences). It showed that their absences decreased after the implementation of the program. The male participants have more absences than female participants.

Before implementation of the feeding program, pupils did not attend classes regularly because it was the season for Durian fruits. They loved to go to the forest rather than attending classes. The pupils shared that "Dikame di durian para kami paka kuwa sa pken ami ka gera paka purot kami sa durian na di ami di pasaan so ped iyan" which means (We are looking for durian so we can eat it and sell the others). Others said they don't find schooling interesting because of poverty. They cannot buy projects and they don't have money to buy food because their parents can only afford their daily basic need for food. Teachers also mentioned that other pupils particularly the female participants reasoned out that they had an illness, toothaches, and fever. It is because some parts of Lanao Del Sur have cold temperatures.

Furthermore, after the implementation of the World Food Program, teachers had records of absences of pupils both male and female participants. They found schooling interesting. They were excited to go to school because of the nutritious breakfast they had. Parents can already give them money for their projects because the allocated budget for their breakfast was saved. Pupils shared that "Pkausosog kami gera pkan kami sa skwelaan ago pka enjoy kami gira pkan kami ago so mga klasmit ami datar kami o di pknik" which means (We had a full tummy at the school and had fun with our classmates like we were just picnicking" etc.). This feedback from pupils showed how they loved this implement feeding program.

The theory of Abraham Maslow (1943) has often been represented in a hierarchical pyramid; one of those was the physiological that includes air, food, water, sex, sleep, and other factors towards homeostasis. One must satisfy the lower-level deficit needs before progressing on to meet higher level growth needs. Poverty, however, has kept generations of families from sending their children to school. Because day-to-day survival must be their priority, poor families often cannot provide children with educational opportunities that could help lift them from destitution.

Table 7. *Nutritional Status (BMI) of the participants before and after the implementation of World Food Program*

Nutritional Status (BMI)	Male				Female			
	Before		After		Before		After	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Severely Wasted	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wasted	3	20%	0	0	2	13.33%	0	0
Normal	12	80%	13	86.67%	13	86.67%	14	93.33%
Overweight	0	0	2	13.33%	0	0	1	6.67%
Obese	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	15	15	100%	100%	15	100%	15	100%

Table 7 presents the nutritional status of both male and female participants before and after the implementation of World Food Program. Result showed that before the program was implemented, 20% or One-Fifth of male participants is under wasted status and 80% or four-fifths of them are within the normal range. For the Female category as to their pre- implementation of WFP, result showed that 13.33% of female participants were considered wasted and 86.67% were in the normal range. While after the implementation of the World Food Program, most of the male participants were in the normal range. Table showed that out of 86.67%, only 13.33% were in the overweight status while 93.33% of female participants were almost in a normal nutritional status.

Teachers said that almost of the pupils were eating vegetables after the feeding program was introduced. It's a great result as they educated them the importance and benefits of eating vegetable. They were having fun seeing their pupils eating joyfully. Pupils shared "So di ami kakan sa walay na sii ami pkataaman" which means (They didn't eat the food they eat from the school).

Furthermore, the result indicated that the pupils under the wasted status both male and female became normal after the implementation. This showed that this feeding program has an improvement on the nutritional status of the participants. Studies highlighted the importance of school feeding programs both as a social safety net for children living in poverty and food insecurity, and as part of the national educational policies and plans. Basing on the views from nutrition experts, pupils with normal nutritional status showed up at school ready to learn. Because of this, an improved nutrition makes pupils healthier, have fewer absences and attend classes more frequently (Clamonte-Alolor 2016).

Table 8. *Enrollment before and after implementations of World Food Program Grade level*

Grade level & Sections	Pupils			Pupils			Indicators
	S.Y 2016-2017		Total	S.Y 2016-2017		Total	
	Male	Female		Male	Female		
Kindergarten	20	21	41	27	34	61	Increasing
Grade I-A	16	18	37	17	24	41	Increasing
Grade I-B	20	18	38	21	15	36	Increasing
Grade II-A	15	20	35	22	25	47	Increasing
Grade II-B	18	24	42	22	21	43	Increasing
Grade III-A	20	23	46	19	27	46	Increasing
Grade III-B	14	25	39	17	22	39	Increasing

Grade IV-A	19	25	44	20	25	45	Increasing
Grade IV-B	13	24	37	14	24	38	Increasing
Grade V-A	18	20	38	19	22	41	Increasing
Grade V-B	15	22	37	19	25	44	Increasing
Grade VI-A	19	25	44	20	27	47	Increasing
Grade VI-B	20	21	41	22	22	44	Increasing

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings derived from the study, the following conclusions were stipulated below: This study showed the efficacy of the World Food Program to the increasing academic performance, attendance, nutritional status, and enrollment of the participants, while the recorded behavior of untoward incidents/misbehaved pupils decreased. This implied that the implementation of this program played a lot on the change of behavior of the pupils.

Based on the findings and the conclusion stated from the study, the following recommendations and future directions are given below: The school heads or principals should encourage all the parents of pupils in Binidayan Elementary School to continuously monitor the nutritional status of their children as feeding has just ended. Teachers may continuously encourage and educate the pupils as well as their parents about the importance of nutrition to the performance of their children not just in their academic performance but also in their health. Parents may extend their full support to school activities like the feeding program as their children see their support from them and closely monitor the academic performance and nutritional status of their children. Future Researchers' study should consider different factors that describe the differences in the implementation of the said program.

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